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BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE *LITTCRIT* – AN INDIAN *RESPONSE TO LITERATURE*

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a bibliometric study of the *LITTCRIT – An Indian Response to Literature* journal for the period from 2011 to 2015 (five years). The purpose of the study is to give a gist of research output in the journal and the content of the coverage in it. The study showed that, out of the 263 published documents, the highest percentage was articles (83.65%). Among the 220 contributors, 56.64% were females and the remaining 102 males (46.36%). The study identified that most of the articles were single authored (94.55%) and the rest by joint authors (6.43%). The degree of collaboration was 0.07. Most of the contributors (94.55%) were from India and 5.45% are foreign contributors. The maximum number of articles were contributed by Asha N Rabb and Bebasree Dattaray (05). More than ten page articles are more (44) and on an average, the *Littcrit* authors have cited over 7.34 references per article. It was found that majority of the authors were from Kerala (46.04%) followed by Delhi (11.80). The study demonstrates the features of the contents of the journal which will be helpful for the publishers to improve the scope of the journal.

Keywords

LITTCRIT – An Indian Response to Literature, Bibliometrics, Authorship pattern, Degree of Collaboration.

INTRODUCTION

The journals are scholarly publications includes articles contributed by research scholars, faculties and scientists and experts, and is related to a particular subject, discipline or field of study. These publications are great sources of current and up- to- date information. The journals are of different types, each with particular purposes and use. They are published in print or online or both the formats. The electronic versions of print journals are e- journals or electronic journals and e- magazines, or it may be journals which exist only in electronic format and have no print editions. They are also called online journals and published many times quicker than their print version journals offer many advantages while conducting research.

Philosophical Transactions is considered as the first scientific journal published in the world by the Royal Society of London in 1665. It established the important principles of scientific priority and peer review, which have become the central foundations of scientific journals ever since [1].The oldest continuously published academic journals from the United States of America was the *English Journal* by the National Council of Teachers of English (NCTE) from 1912.

The term bibliometrics was coined by Alan Pritchard 1969, in his paper titled *statistical bibliography or bibliometrics*. He defined the term as “the application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other media of communication” [2]. It is generally termed as statistical analysis of written publications; such as books or articles. The commonly used bibliometric methods are citation analysis and content analysis and are frequently used in the discipline of library and information science, including scientometrics. Bibliometric techniques applied to single journals will help to identify the trend of research of a particular area of research includes: subject distribution, contributor’s year- wise distribution, pattern of authorship and collaborative research, ranking of authors etc. In this study an attempt has been made to bibliometric ally analyse the literature published in the *LITTCRIT* journal for the years 2011 to 2015.

OBJECTIVES

Following are the main objectives of the study.

- To examine year-wise analysis of contributions

- To examine category-wise distribution of papers
- To study the subject analysis of contributors
- To examine the pattern of authorship
- To calculate the degree of collaboration
- To identify the most prolific contributors
- To examine citation pattern
- Geographical distributions of the authors.

METHODOLOGY

The study is on the journal *LITTCRIT-an Indian response to literature* for the years 2011 to 2015. The data consists of year of publication with its volume number, number of authors with their affiliations and its geographical location, length of articles etc. The data was downloaded on MS Excel sheets and was analysed based on the objectives. All the collected data were analyzed using simple calculations and bibliometric techniques. It's estimated that a total number of 263 contributions are covered during the period of study.

ABOUT LITTCRIT

LITTCRIT: An Indian response to literature is a peer reviewed international journal published half-yearly from Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala. Prof. P. K. Rajan, former Vice Chancellor, Kannur University, Kerala was the founder editor of the journal, which was started in 1975. It seeks to reflect Indian responses to literature in general and has focus on select literary themes of national importance [3]. While representing different schools of literary criticism, it has preference for literary studies which search for aesthetic dimensions rising from the organic inter relationship between literature and social life. It also promotes theoretical inquiries with a historical orientation relating to the problems of literature and the arts. Every year one issue will be multi- thematic in nature, and the other will focus on a general theme of contemporary relevance. The circulation profile of *Littcrit* includes academics, writers, students, colleges, universities and libraries throughout India and abroad. The present study attempts to quantitatively assess the contributions in the *Littcrit*, the Indian referred English language journal for the period 2011 – 2015.

REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES

The purpose of the study by Giménez-Espert and Prado-Gascó [4] was to bibliometric analysis of the six nursing journals indexed in the Science Citation Index (Web of Science). During 2012-2017, the study showed that 11371 authors contributed 3937 articles from 2980 institutions and 84 countries. Yu, Xu and Antuchevičienė [5] used the method of bibliometric to study the status and development trends of the journal. Information was collected from the Science Citation Index (SCI) database. The paper explored the internal structure and development trend of the JCEM journal.

Gupta and Hasan [6] in their paper studied the journal *Metamorphosis: A Journal of Management Research* during the year 2002-2016 and analysed 200 research articles. The study focused on various aspects of the contents of the journal. Bibliometric analysis of the *IIM Kozhikode Society and Management Review* (2012-2018) has been conducted by Aiswaria and Sudhier [7]. Bibliometric analysis of the journal *Information Processing & Management* was conducted by Abdi, Idris, Alguliyev and Alguliyev [8] for the period 1980-2015. The findings of the study includes the summary of research activity and characterize its most important aspects. Raza and Malik [9] examined the *Journal of Knowledge Management*, to study the bibliographic form of contributions, publication pattern, highly cited papers and top ranked countries. The study conducted during 2009-2016 includes 508 papers from 57 countries and 1214 authors. Brahma and Verma [10] studied *Malaysian Journal of Library and Information Science* during the period 2007-2016. Malaysia was identified as the top ranked country with 31.17% contributions, followed by India and Iran. The most productive author was A.N. Zainabis with 19 contributions and the most productive institute was University of Malaya with 63 publications.

Kumar and Verma [11] studied citation pattern of the *Journal for Decision Makers*. They found that the contributors are preferred printed documents for their research work. Researchers preferred print documents than online. Sankar and Kavitha [12] brought out the results of a bibliometric analysis of *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation* for the period 2005-2015. Velmurugan and Radhakrishnan [13] conducted a scientometric study of *Malaysian Journal of Library and Information Science*. They described that the highest numbers of contributions (75.36 per cent) were from joint authors and rest 24.64 per cent contributions were single authored.

Mulla and Dhanamjaya [14] studied *SRELS Journal of Information Management* during 2000-2009. The study found that, out of total 686 contributors, 360 (52.48%) are contributed by joint authored paper (43.69%). Krishnaswamy and Jesintha [15] conducted bibliometric analysis of *Annals of Library and Information Studies* for a period of six years. Single author

contributors are more during the period of study (59.96 %.). Swain, Swain and Rautry [16] studied the publications pattern of the journal *Business Economics*(2008- 2013). The journal publishes papers in the form of articles, reviews, editorials, and conference papers. Harith and Singh [17] studied bibliometric components of contributors in the *Indian Journal of International Law*. The study covers the quantitative growth of articles by volume and year, per article and other bibliometric indicators.

Allik [18] carried out a study on the *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* during the 2001 -2010. Bansal [19] in his study on the *DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology*, discussed different parameters of a single journal bibliometric study. A study on the *Journal of Documentation* was conducted by Tsay and Shu [20]. They discussed the features of the content of the journal.

Bibliometric analysis of *Annals of Library and Information Studies* (2002-2006) was carried out by Chaurasia [21] and showed a trend of growth in contributions during the period of study. Casilas and Acedo [22] studied the performance of a subfield in the field of management business through the journal *Family Business Review*. During 1988-2005, the average number of references per paper was 29.7 citations. Wang, Wang and Weldon [23] studied the internationalization of China's English-language scientific journals based on their various parameters. Batthini and Madani [24] in their bibliometric study on the *Journal of Entrepreneurship* found that majority of the contributions were from India.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Bibliographic Forms of Contributions

It is found that the journal publishes papers in the form of articles, book reviews, film reviews etc. The table 1 shows that more than 80% of the contributions in the journal are in the form of articles (220) followed by book reviews (11.41%).

Table 1: Bibliographic forms of Contributions

SI. No	Bibliographic Forms	Number	Percentage
1	Editorial	5	01.90

2	Articles	202	83.65
3	Film Reviews	5	01.90
4	Book Reviews	30	11.41
5	Readers Column	3	01.14
Total		263	100.00

Year- wise Distribution of Articles

The table2 provides chronological distribution of publications in the journal. The analysis reveals that there are 202articles from 10 issues, out of which the highest number 48 (23.7%) are published in the year 2015 and the least number of 33 (16.3%) in the year 2011. The table also reveals that the distribution of articles is not consistent in each year. The range of articles published per year during the period under study is between 33 and 48.The average article per issue was found 10.1.

Table 2:Year- wise Distribution of Articles

Year	Volume	No. of Articles		Total Articles	Percentage
		Issue 1	Issue 2		
2011	37	14	19	33	16.33
2012	38	17	19	36	17.82
2013	39	29	17	46	22.77
2014	40	20	19	39	19.31
2015	41	26	22	48	23.76
Total		106	96	202	100.00

Subject-wise distribution of Articles

The subject wise analysis of articles published in the journal is shown in the table 3.

Table 3:Subject- wise distribution of Articles

Sl. No.	Subject	Frequency	Percentage
1	Literature	46	22.77
2	Film Studies	35	17.36
3	Psychology	25	12.37
4	Cultural studies	18	8.91
5	Feminism	17	8.41
6	Historical studies	7	3.46
7	Indian Literature	7	3.46
8	Others	47	23.26
Total		202	100.00

Out of the 202 articles published in *Littcrit*, 46 articles (22.77%) belongs to the area of ‘literature’ followed by ‘film studies’ with 35 articles(17.36%) and ‘psychology’ 25 articles (12.37%). It is found that 8.91 % contributions are in the area of ‘cultural studies’ and the 23.26 % of the total contributions are in the other of subject areas.

Page- wise distribution

Table 4 presents the length of articles published in *Littcrit*. Major portion of articles i.e., 44 are having 10 or more pages, followed by 36 articles in 7 pages. It is interesting to note that there is no one pagearticle publishedin the journal. It is found that, out of the 202 articles, only 4 are having 2 pages and 13 articles with 3 pages. It is also found that an article published in the year 2013 has the maximum length of 51 pages.

Table 4: Length of the articles

Year	Length of Contributions										Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10>=	
2011	0	1	2	11	5	9	6	4	2	7	47

2012	0	0	3	6	4	6	7	6	1	9	42
2013	0	3	3	6	5	8	7	6	3	10	51
2014	0	0	1	5	1	6	7	6	2	7	35
2015	0	0	4	6	6	4	9	5	0	11	45
Total	0	4	13	34	21	33	36	27	8	44	202

Authorship pattern

Table 5 gives the details about the authorship pattern with number of articles contributed by authors in the journal. The study depicts that out of total contributions, 191 articles (94.55%) are single author papers and the share of two author papers are 13 (6.43 %). It is interesting to note that there is only one article with three authors.

Table 5: Authorship pattern of articles

Degree of Collaboration

Year	Single Author	%	Two Authors	%	Three Authors	Total Articles	Total no. of Authors
2011	29	15.18	4	30.77	0	33	37
2012	34	17.80	2	15.39	0	36	38
2013	44	23.04	3	23.08	0	46	50
2014	41	21.46	0	0	0	39	41
2015	43	22.52	4	30.76	1	48	54
Total	191	94.55	13	6.43	1	202	220

It can be defined as the ratio of the number of collaborative research papers to the total number of research papers in the discipline during a given period of time. It is calculated by Subramanyam [25] formula:

$$C = N_m / N_m + N_s$$

where C is degree of collaboration in discipline,

N_m is number of multi-authored papers, and

N_s is number of single authored papers.

From the table 6, it is found that the highest value of degree of collaboration (DC), 1.00 was observed in the year 2014 and the least value of 0.11 in the year 2011. There are fluctuations in the degree of collaboration, and the overall value is 0.07 during the period of study.

Table 6: Degree of Collaboration

Year	Single author	Two authors	Three authors	Total authors	DC
2011	29	4	0	33	0.11
2012	34	2	0	36	0.94
2013	44	3	0	47	0.96
2014	41	0	0	41	1.00
2015	43	4	1	48	0.89
Total	191	13	1	202	0.07

Author per Article

The following table 8 gives the average author per article published in the journal.

Table 8: Author per article

Year	Total No. of Articles	No. of Authors	Average Author per Article	Productivity per Author
2011	33	37	1.12	0.89
2012	36	38	1.05	0.95
2013	46	50	1.09	0.92
2014	39	41	1.05	0.95

2015	48	54	1.13	0.89
Total	202	220	1.09	0.92

It is found that the average author per article in the journal *Litterit* is 1.09 and it varies from different issues and years. The value is more in the years 2011 (1.12) and 2015 (1.13). The productivity per author is found to be 0.92 throughout the period and is maximum in the year 2012.

Number of Citations of Articles

In order to ascertain the number of citations appended in each article, the total number of articles and their citations are calculated. (table 9).

Table 9: Distribution of Citations

Year	No. of Articles			No. of Citations			Average No. of Citations per Article
	Issue 1	Issue 2	Total	Issue 1	Issue 2	Total	
2011	14	19	33	124	159	283	8.57
2012	17	19	36	129	116	245	6.80
2013	29	17	46	190	176	366	7.95
2014	20	19	39	89	144	233	5.97
2015	26	22	48	164	192	356	7.42
Total			202			1,483	7.34

It is found that, 202 articles appended 1,483 citations and the average number of citations per article throughout period is found as 7.34. The maximum value is in the year 2011 (8.57) and the minimum in the year 2014 (5.97). It is also found that the average citations from article varied from 5.97 to 8.57.

India v/s Foreign Authors

Table 10 shows the contributor's geographical affiliation. Out of 220 authors, a maximum of 208 authors are from India (94.55%) and only 12 authors are from abroad (5.45%). It is found that there were no foreign author contributions in the year 2011 and a maximum of five

contributions in the year 2014. During the period of study, majority of the contributions are from India (94.55%).

Table 10: India vs Foreign Authors

Year	Indian	%	Foreign	%	Total
2011	37	100.00	0	0.00	37
2012	36	94.74	2	5.26	38
2013	48	96.00	2	5.26	50
2014	36	87.80	5	12.19	41
2015	51	94.44	3	5.56	54
Total	208	94.55	12	5.45	220

Ranking of Authors

Ranked list of most prolific contributors are shown in the table 11.

Table 11: Ranked list of prolific authors

Sl. No.	Name of the Author	No. of Articles	Rank
1	Asha N. Rabb	5	1
2	DebasreeDattaray	5	1
3	Hariharan B	3	2
4	Chithra V R	3	2
5	John Oliver Perry	3	2
6	Sujatha S	3	2
7	Dasan A S	2	3
8	Ajay Sekhar	2	3
9	Issac Sebastian	2	3

10	Divya N	2	3
11	Sachithanandan K	2	3
12	Lal C A	2	3
13	Murali Krishna	2	3
14	Ajayakumar P P	2	3
15	PromodL S	2	3
16	Ritu Sen	2	3
17	Singh R K	2	3
18	Sony R Jayaraj	2	3
19	Sajitha	2	3
20	Vincent B Netto	2	3
21	Umar N	2	3

The most prolific authors are Asha N Rabb and Debasree Dattaray, who contributed 5 articles each followed by Hariharan,B., Chitra V R., John Oliver Perry and Sujatha S with 3 articles each during the five year period. Fifteen authors contributed 2 articles each followed by 150 authors with one article only.

Gender- wise Distribution of Contributors

The gender wise analysis of the authors is shown in the table 12. It was identified that, out of the 220 authors, majority of them are (56.64 %)female and46.36% are female contributors.The maximum number of male authors are in the year 2013 (60%) and the females are in the year 2012 (62.16%).

Table 12: Gender-wise distribution

Year	Male	%	Female	%	Total
2011	17	45.95	20	54.05	37
2012	14	37.84	23	62.16	37
2013	30	60.00	20	40.00	50
2014	20	42.55	27	57.45	47

2015	21	42.86	28	57.14	49
Total	102	46.36	118	56.64	220

Category-wise Distribution of Authors

Table 13: Categories of contributors

Sl. No.	Category	No. of Papers	Percentage
1	Research Scholars	42	20.79
2	Assistant Professor	87	43.07
3	Associate Professor	46	22.79
4	Others	27	13.36
Total		202	100.00

The distribution of authors based on their designations and positions are shown in the table 13. The table reveals that majority of the contributors are Assistant Professors (43.07%) followed by Associative Professors (22.79%) and Research Scholars (20.79%) respectively. The authors from other categories contributed 27 (13.36%) articles, and they includes-poets, students and readers.

Geographical Distribution

The table 14 shows the state- wise distribution of authors during the five-year period. It shows that, the majority of contributors are from Kerala with 93 articles (46.04%) followed by Delhi and Haryana with 24(11.80%) and 17(8.41%) articles respectively. The study revealed that the authors from 22 states have contributed in the journal and hence it is well represented nationally.

Table 14: State-wise Distribution of Articles

Sl No.	State	No. of Articles	Percentage
1	Kerala	93	46.04
2	Tamil Nadu	13	6.40
3	Delhi	24	11.80
4	Karnataka	9	4.45

5	Haryana	17	8.41
6	Rajasthan	7	3.40
7	Maharashtra	13	6.43
8	Punjab	11	5.44
9	Uttar Pradesh	4	1.98
10	West Bengal	2	0.90
11	Arunachal Pradesh	3	1.40
12	Andhra Pradesh	6	2.90
Total		202	100.00

CONCLUSION

The number of journals shows the literature growth indicator in any field of knowledge and they are considered as the main channel for transmitting knowledge. The bibliometric analysis of journals helps to determine the relationships within a literature and describing a literature. It also helps to understand the communication flow among the literature. This study describes and analyses the various factors including the bibliometric components of the contributions in the *Littcrit: An Indian Response to Literature*. It is confined to five years of the journal issues from 2011 to 2015 containing 10 issues and the analysis has been done purely on quantitative methods based on bibliometric techniques. The paper covers the quantitative growth of articles by volume and year, distribution of citations, range and percentage of citations per article, authorship pattern, ranked list of most prolific contributors, geographical distribution of authors etc.

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